

Date: 17-March-2025, **Time:** 10:00-11:00, **Location:** online,

Participants: Expertise center, sounding board members

Appendix to read and comment during the meeting: <https://zenodo.org/records/14931647>

Agenda

10:00- 10:10 Welcome and explanation of purpose of sounding board group

10:10 -10:20 Introduction round

10:20- 10:40 Presentation Expertise center and plans for 2025

10:40-10:55 Questions and remarks

10:55 -11:00 Any other business.

- [DIAMAS conference](#), Brussel, BE, 3rd June
- [OASPA, Leuven](#), BE, 22-24 September

Highlighted Meeting notes

- The terms “professionalization” and IPSPS can alienate our target groups consider other terms such as “operational” and “Diamond”.
Action: Expertise center will ensure we use inclusive terms.
- How are we measuring and defining success?
Answer: We have various reporting lines in which we provide a short overview of our work. In addition, we also track visitors, subscribers, attendees for all events/ resources/website/social media etc.
- Are there any plans towards sustainability of the expertise center? The Nordic Capacity Center is asking for funding from national bodies.
Answer: We will develop a sustainability plan and possible options on how the expertise center can continue next year.
- *Suggestion from the expertise center: It would be extremely beneficial for all emerging capacity centers if they could meet. One option will be to have a satellite meeting of all capacity’s centers either at the DIAMAS conference or at the OASPA. This will be followed up separately.*
- Other ideas for resources to create: “How to flip your book series?”, “How to flip your IPSPs?”.